

HYPERKALAEMIA AND HAEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS: ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC CHANGES

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ABSTRACT

Background – Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) present hydro-electrolytic alterations due to the lack of adequate regulation of the internal medium. Of these alterations hyperkalaemia is frequent and produce neuromuscular symptoms, electrocardiographic changes and arrhythmias. Literature affirms that patients with ESRD present less prominent hyperkalaemia-related electrocardiographic changes than those patients with normal renal function.

Objectives: To evaluate electrocardiographic alterations related with potassium in our ESRD patients and to compare the obtained results with those previously reported.

Methods: Descriptive, cross-sectional and prospective study in hospital haemodialysis (HD) patients. Pre- and post-HD serum potassium and other electrolyte concentrations were measured, and simultaneous 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) obtained at the first session of the week. An expert evaluated all ECG's.

Results: 39 patients were included in the study, 58.9% were women and 41.1% men, with a mean age 67.35 years (24-89). Serum potassium pre-HD range was 2.8 to 7.4 mEq/l (mean 5.07 mEq/L), 29.4% of the sample presented levels ≥ 5.5 mEq/l and the most frequent alteration in the ECG was high and peaked T waves in leads V2 to V4. In the hyperkalaemia cases, the mean elevation of T wave was 7mm. In 2 hyperkalaemia patients there was no elevation of T wave: one T wave was negative ($K^+ = 6$ mEq/L) and another one stayed normal ($K^+ = 5.6$ mEq/L).

Conclusions: The ECG continues to be a good tool of early hyperkalaemia detection, contributing to estimating severity. Patients with ESRD present electrocardiographic alterations similar to the healthy population.

Keywords: Hyperkalaemia; Electrocardiogram; Arrhythmias; Haemodialysis; Nursing.

INTRODUCTION

Potassium is the most important intracellular electrolyte. It is the principal cell cation forming part of the absorption system in the organism and its blood level affects all types of neuromuscular activities. Many signs and symptoms of potassium excess (hyperkalaemia) come from the cardiovascular, central nervous and muscular systems. The potassium balance is regulated in the kidneys, therefore most of the potassium loss from the organism occurs through urine (1,2).

Patients with end stage renal disease (ESRD) display a number of hydroelectrolytic alterations due to a lack of internal medium regulation, a fundamental function of the kidney. Of these alterations, hyperkalaemia can be a frequent complication showing neuromuscular symptoms, electrocardiographic changes and cardiac arrhythmias (3,4). As the hyperkalaemia worsens, potentially fatal electrocardiographic changes occur and alterations in cardiac conduction appear in peaked T-waves; prolonged P-R interval, QRS-wave and QT interval; flattening and absence of P-wave, bradycardia and ventricular arrhythmias (5).

Determining serum levels of this electrolyte in the laboratory can take some time. As results arrive, the electrocardiographic monitoring (6) and documenting of the symptoms, which the patients display at that moment, can prove very useful. An electrocardiogram (ECG) can be a very useful diagnostic tool if the professional knows the changes that can occur in abnormal situations (3).

In addition, muscular weakness and tiredness can be present, although these signs are not definitive since a haemodialysis patient can display weakness that is due to multiple causes (7,8). Similarly, diverse publications (6-9) have reached a conclusion that patients with ESRD tolerate hyperkalaemia better, displaying fewer arrhythmias and neuromuscular signs than persons with normal renal function.

Also, the serum potassium level sometimes does not correspond with clinical or electrocardiographic alterations. As orientative data, all hyperkalaemia above 5.5 mEq/L can be potentially fatal (10). A fast restoration and the coexistence of hypocalcaemia or hyponatraemia favour complications of hyperkalaemia.

Bearing in mind the existing controversies on the subject and the opportunity to care for patients with ESRD, who presumably have elevated serum potassium levels before coming to haemodialysis, we have set out to determine and to relate electrocardiographic changes with elevated serum potassium levels in patients with ESRD being treated with haemodialysis (HD).

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive, transversal and prospective study was carried out on 36 patients who were treated in the Nephrology Service of the University Hospital Marqués de Valdecilla of Santander.

Patients with ESRD receiving HD as renal replacement therapy (RRT) for more than 2 months, who were over 18 years of age and consented to participate in the study were included. Those who did not fulfill these requisites were excluded.

The collection of data was carried out from 1st January to 1st February 2005. The task was performed by 5 people from the investigation team, following norms of Good Clinical Practice. The study was carried out on the patient's first treatment day of the week because on this day it was highly probable that the patients had elevated serum potassium levels. Conventional dialysis was carried out 3 times per week, without previous warning to the patients of the start date of the study.

In order to collect the data, a register based on the existing references was designed. Data was taken from the non-computerized Clinical History of each patient. The four study variables were:

1. Demographic data: age, sex, nephropathy type, diseases and cardiovascular factors risk, and treatment.

2. Biochemical parameters: nephrology profile (urea, creatinine, glucose, CO₂, chlorine, sodium, potassium and calcium) previous and subsequent to the haemodialysis treatment, in the Nephrology laboratory. The biochemical parameters were determined with an autoanalyzer CX3 Synchron Delta (Beckton, USA), validated for the Spanish population (11). All the ionic parameters were measured by the indirect ISE (ions selective electrodes) method (12), and for creatinine the Jaffé method (13) was used.

3. Electrocardiographic registers: A simultaneous 12-lead standard electrocardiogram (ECG) was obtained before and after the haemodialysis, which registered: cardiac frequency, rate, P-wave, PR-interval, duration and amplitude of complex QRS, T-wave and arrhythmias.

All ECGs were read by one of the investigators who had no prior knowledge of the serum potassium level, and the amplitude of T-wave was measured, in each patient, before and after HD. Later, the difference between the different waves was reduced before the HD and after the same HD. The derivations in intercostal spaces were conserved to avoid a different positioning and, as consequence, a different morphology that contaminated the changes in the layouts that might have appeared, which is why we used self-adhesive electrodes throughout the treatment.

4. We asked patients about signs and symptoms which presented before the HD.

RESULTS

There were a total of 36 patients, of whom 2 were excluded, as their cognitive level did not allow them to give their consent nor fulfil the conditions necessary to obtain an ECG that could be valued optimally. Of the 34 patients who were included in the study, the average age was 68 years old (range: 24 - 89 years), of whom 47% were men and 53% women. The predominant Nephropathy type was vascular, followed by diverse diseases, which can be observed in graph 1.

Graph 1. Nephropaty type

80% were treated with standard hemodialysis and 20% with haemodiafiltration on-line (HDF on-line). The most common dialyzer used was polyacrylonitrile (41,9%), followed by polysulfone and cellulose diacetate (29%).

47% had previous cardiovascular diseases, the most common being ischemic cardiopathy along with intermittent claudication (11.7%) and cardiac insufficiency (8.7%). In reference to factors of cardiovascular risk, 91% had hypertension, followed by diabetes (32.4%), hyperlipemia (23.4%) and obesity (17.6%).

Predialysis serum potassium levels stayed between 2.8 and 7.4 mEq/l (mean 5.07 mEq/L). 29.4% displayed levels \geq 5.5mEq/l. Post HD, the patients displayed serum potassium levels between 2.2 and 4.3 mEq/L. The pre-dialysis mean value for calcium was of 8.8mg/dl and the mean value of sodium was 136.32 mEq/L. The rest of the parameters can be observed and compared in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Biochemical most relevant results for the study obtained pre haemodialysis.

Parameter	Unit	Normal Ranges	Mean	Medium	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation
Urea	g/L	0.1-0.5	1.50	1.47	1.05	0.88	2.45	0.405
Creatinine	mg/dl	0.5-1.4	7.4	7.7	4.6	3.2	13	2.59
Sodium	mEq/L	135-145	136.3	136.5	136	126	147	5.09
Potassium	mEq/L	3.5-5.0	5.07	5.1	3.7	2.8	7.4	1.04
Calcium	mg/dl	8.4-10.4	8.8	8.7	9	7	12	0.94

Table 2. Biochemical most relevant results for the study obtained post haemodialysis.

Parameter	Unit	Normal Ranges	Mean	Medium	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation
Urea	g/L	0.1-0.5	0.46	0.47	0.45	0.20	0.85	0.15
Creatinine	mg/dl	0.5-1.4	3.1	2.9	2.4	1.20	9.2	1.50
Sodium	mEq/L	135-145	136.9	138	139	126	143	4.2
Potassium	mEq/L	3.5-5.0	3.21	3.20	3.20	2.20	4.30	0.47
Calcium	mg/dl	8.4-10.4	9.75	9.75	9.00	7.9	11.4	0.95

In regard to the electrocardiographic analysis, before the procedure 61.8% of the patients were in sinus rate. Of the cardiac arrhythmias detected, auricular fibrillation is notable as being present in 17.6% of the patients. The cardiac frequency average was 78.38 beats/minute. In 55.9% cases there were no P wave alterations, whereas in more than 17%, a decrease in the voltage was observed. Referring to the QRS complex, the majority did not have any alteration (58.8%). 44.1% presented some type of intraventricular branch block and no patient presented cardiovascular symptomatology previous or subsequent to the procedure. As we can observe in graph 2, in the cases of hyperkalaemia, the elevation of T waves was 7mm, except in 2 cases. Firstly, in one case the T wave is negative (K= 6 mEq/L) and in the other it remains at a normal measurement (5,6 K= mEq/L). (Fig.1 and 2).

Graphic 2: Hyperkalaemia cases: T wave elevation pre and post HD. Potassium serum levels are in mEq/L unit.

Graphic 3: No hyperkalaemia cases: T wave elevation pre and post HD. Potassium serum levels are in mEq/L unit.

Figure 1: The electrocardiogram present a cardiac frequency of 75 beats per minute: 1st grade atrial-ventricular block appear (), piked T wave more than 10 mm (), and left branch block image () (Serum potassium level: 9 mEq/l.).

Figure 2: The electrocardiogram showed a normal rate (90 beats per minute). Left branch block and 1st atrial-ventricular block had disappeared. The electrocardiogram is normalized (serum potassium level 4 mEq/l.).

The derivations in which we most frequently see the elevation of the T wave are V2, V3, and V4, with V3 being the most common. After HD, 90% of the cases with hyperkalaemia present a standardized T wave, as is observed in graph 3. However in the remaining 10%, it descends by 4 mm, and the T wave remains higher than normal.

In those cases where patients display normal serum potassium levels, the changes in T wave are different. After HD it normalises at 39%, whilst in the rest of the cases: 21.7% diminish considerably, 26% remain equal and 13% become negative.

With regard to post HD electrocardiographic analysis it should be pointed out that 64.7% are in sinus rate; with an average cardiac frequency of 78.38 beats per minute, ranging between 60 and 140 beats per minute. In 70.6% of the cases no alteration of the P wave was observed and 85.3% displayed a QRS complex of normal characteristics. 44.1% of the patients displayed some type of the intraventricular branch block and in 8.7% of the cases the U wave appeared.

DISCUSSION

Currently, the most frequent cause of mortality in patients with ESRD is cardiovascular disease, ischemic cardiopathy, arrhythmias and especially cerebrovascular accidents. These patients display a high prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors like hypertension (HT), diabetes, dyslipemia, and a process of atheromatosis accelerated by the uremic state (1).

In order to explain the type of electrocardiographic changes, it is advisable to indicate that the appearance of small increases of extracellular potassium shortens the duration of the transmembrane potential action, increasing the speed of repolarisation in phase 3. This entails the visualization in the ECG of peaked T waves with a narrow base (T waves in a "tent" shape) (8). As the potassium increases further, potential for rest is reduced (it becomes less negative), which in turn leads to a decrease in the speed of the inscription of phase 0. In this situation, the auriculo-ventricular and intra-ventricular conduction are delayed, extending the PR interval and the QRS complex thus becoming wider. (Fig.1 and 2). Progressive increases of potassium (from 7.5 mEq/l) make the auricular muscle unresponsive to a greater or lesser extent, possibly producing varying degrees of blockage in the sino-auricular or in other levels and perhaps even asistole. It is also possible to find alterations in the conduction (14) and ectopic rates, which is sometimes difficult to interpret and among which we find ventricular tachycardia or pseudo-tachycardia, a complicated and difficult diagnosis (15). Therefore, the ECG reflects with remarkable precision both acute coronary ischemia (16) and the effects of progressively increasing levels of extracellular potassium (17) on modifying the ST segment and T wave. In fact, acute coronary ischemia and hyperkalaemia are included in the differential electrocardiographic diagnosis when such modifications (18) take place. Rarely do they present a diagnostic problem, since coronary ischemia and hyperkalaemia take place in quite different contexts and are easily identifiable. Only in the case of them occurring at the same time (acute coronary ischemia

during hyperkalaemia) could they affect the ECG waves and, possibly, provoke the appearance of arrhythmias.

In our case, as was to be expected, after HD the urea and creatinine figures decreased sharply (the principal aim of this treatment is to purify the blood of waste substances). Sodium hardly varies since it is an ion that is eliminated through other corporal fluids and it is not accumulated in excess in this type of patient. In reference to calcium, in another publication (14) the serum level has an inverse relationship with the amplitude of the T wave. In the subjects of the study, the calcium diminished slightly due to the secondary hyperparathyroidism to the ESRD; these pre haemodialysis levels cannot be evaluated by severe hypocalcaemia due to the drug treatment. In addition this parameter increases slightly because of the dialysate composition after the haemodialysis.

Other authors have published that high potassium levels in the blood do not include changes in the ECG, mainly in the amplitude of T wave (3,19). We differ, finding in the majority of cases a relationship between high potassium levels and increase of amplitude in electrocardiographic T wave and other alterations. Nevertheless, we cannot affirm it categorically, because we would need to make a study with a greater number of patients. Although there is no scientific data to support it, it is probable that the population that does not suffer ESRD and that has never had hyperkalaemia even if, for any reason, they had an important increase in potassium level could have more visible and quicker ECG changes. We think that the number of episodes of hyperkalaemia suffered by an individual is inversely proportional to the magnitude of the electrocardiographic changes, probably due to factors of adaptability making them less susceptible to situations of greater risk.

It would be recommendable to have a base ECG, so that before the clinical presumption of hyperkalaemia we could compare the layout of the ECG while the serum potassium is analysed, and visualize changes or arrhythmias to initiate speedy treatment (20). Not only blood pressure but the standardization of physical examinations is of great importance. The evaluation of the central cardiac frequency is important, since a majority of HD patients display cardiovascular problems, with the possible appearance of arrhythmias and the subsequent life threatening risk for the patient.

CONCLUSIONS

We can affirm that the elevated potassium levels alter the amplitude of T waves (high and peaked waves), which is why the ECG continues to be a useful tool of early detection of hyperkalaemia. Patients with ESRD display electrocardiographic alterations similar to those of the healthy population.

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